

Horizon 2020

Research and Innovation Framework Program

CHESSETUP

Deliverable 7.1

Detailed Communication and Dissemination Plan

Deliverable Type:	Public
Date:	12/08/2016
Distribution:	All WP
Editors:	Edenway
Contributors:	WP7

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 680556.

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Document history

Date	Version	Editor	Change	Status
29/07/2016	1	Edenway		Creation
12/08/2016	2	Edenway	Appendix	Delivered

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1. Summary

CHESSE SETUP (Combined HEat Supply System by using Solar Energy and heat pUmPs), is part of the implementation program financed by the “Horizon 2020 – Research and Innovation Framework” programme of the European Commission. The project started on July 2016, and will last 36 months.

The present document will introduce the very essence of the project and its engineering process. Besides assessing dissemination of the results and stakeholder engagement are central to the success of CHESSE SETUP, this document will also shape a detailed communication plan and a dissemination guideline. The CHESSE SETUP consortium recognises that dissemination activities are an essential and pervasive activity throughout the project’s life, and that each of its members may contribute to it. The present Plan aims to detail the strategy to broadcast CHESSE SETUP messages to its public but also the ways to obtain feedback from its audience.

CHESSE SETUP communication plan’s creed may be “first raise awareness, then disseminate achievements” as it was introduced throughout the kick off meeting (Barcelona, 07/07/2016). Thus, the following document will extract the essence of the project’s goals, the philosophy and challenges lying behind it. It will define the key messages to spread, identify the stakeholders, the best communication channels to reach them, and finally the tools that will ensure the dissemination’s efficiency.

CHESSE SETUP is an achieved project, enhancing other European projects’ results on very technical fields (selection of the heat pumps, storage materials of the tank, configurations of the system components...). As a consequence, the knowledges gained from the implementation will be very valuable for high level technical expertise stakeholders. However, the dissemination plan aims to target a wider range of stakeholders and will seek to adapt the reports’ content to non-technical recipients that could also become possible implementers of the CHESSE SETUP recommendations.

If it is vital to develop a communication strategy, covering internal as well as external purposes, intermittent events and long-lasting processes. Nevertheless, a communication plan has to be conceived as an evolving guideline, and we may assume that it is going to expand throughout the achievements’ emergence and contingency events.

2. Project overview

This section focuses on the project itself and emphasizes its outlines. As a first part, it may answer the following questions;

- What is CHESSE SETUP?
- Why developing this project?
- How will CHESSE SETUP be carried out?
- Who are the actors committed behind CHESSE SETUP?

2.1. Project content

By the time when heating and domestic hot water (DHW) represent 60% of the energy consumed in our dwellings, Chess Set Up is implementing a centralized system that would be able to supply this demand all year-long, and even more.

In fact, Chess Set Up relies on the combined use of various existing technologies on site: hybrid photovoltaic and solar thermal (PV-ST) panels, seasonal thermal storage tanks and heat pumps. This set of tools will allow the dwellings to be heating and DHW self-sufficient during the sunny months, and to rely on their heat reserves the rest of the year.

This heating system would be sustainable, with a very low ecological footprint, as the heat pump will be supplied by the energy produced by the PV-ST panels – or other sustainable back-up sources such as biomass or heat waste. The project will also explore the possibility to integrate the system with other electricity or cooling technologies

Figure 1- Seasonal operation of the system

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The project will also develop its own software, in order to generate a global monitoring of the system, according to numerous criteria such as the climate zone or the specificity of the building. CHESSE SETUP deals as well with Smart Grids: thanks to a control and management system taking into account some external factors such as the electricity price, the system could choose whether to activate the heat pump, or to turn to the grid.

In order to particularize, and to industrialize a general pattern, a business model will arise from every three pilots which are;

- A small-scale prototype in Lavola's headquarters in Manlleu (Catalonia, Spain),
- 50 new dwellings located in Corby (England),
- A new sport centre in Sant Cugat (Catalonia, Spain).

The system developed by Chess Set Up would be a solution to reach the European objectives of "New Zero Energy Building" (NZEB), at an individual or district level, taking into account that the building sector accounts for 40% of the energy needs.

Furthermore, this system would be suitable to new buildings as well as existent ones, as demonstrated by two of the pilots, and provide retrofitting solutions.

Figure 2- Investment cost of seasonal storage system compared to other European projects

2.2. Main objectives and general philosophy

As an innovation project, CHESSE SETUP aims to implement various precise hypothesis, to adapt them to the use cases' local circumstances, to modulate the system in order to improve it or overcome possible obstacles. From empirical findings, conclusions will be drawn.

Beyond this precise scientific objectives, CHESSE SETUP could not be overlooked without the European Horizon 2020 purposes. From this point of view, the program is a chain-link, powering a common project: sustainable development.

2.2.1. Immediate objectives

As mentioned before, Chess Set Up aims to enhance the systems developed by other European research programs. The main innovation is the combination of photovoltaic-solar thermal panels connected both with the heat pump and the thermal storage system.

Implement a new heating solution based on a trio of technologies on a seasonal mode - hybrid photovoltaic-thermal solar panels, a thermal storage system and heat pump.

Improve the initial system, and make it compatible with renewable energies' back up sources.

Test and monitor the functioning of this system in different geographical situations and type of building, along 3 use cases and thanks to a proper software.

Draw business models from the use cases in order to industrialize CHESSETUP's achievements.

Reduce the peak of electricity demand, relying on the system inertia, and allow the renewable energies' connection to the grid.

Propose an efficient and practical solution to build NZEB, relying on renewable energy sources and efficiency of the materials.

2.2.2. Further goals

CHESSETUP is closely linked with the European Horizon 2020 work program. If the heating sector has been neglected in the energy policy debate, we currently know this sector represents 60% of the building sector energy's needs. Hence, ignoring the heating sector could threaten the European energy policy goals (see energy and climate package voted in 2008).

While implementing a heating system relying mainly on a combination of an energy storage solution and PV-ST solar panels on site, able to spill the surplus electricity to the local grid,

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and using a low carbon footprint heat pump, CHESSE SETUP is working for the three facets of the 2020 Program.

Furthermore, the Energy Performance Building Directive (EPBD, 2010) provides that by 2020, all new buildings (2018 for occupied and owned by public authorities) should reach “nearly zero-energy” performance levels using innovative, cost-optimal technologies with integration of renewable energy sources on site or nearby. Then, providing new retrofitting solutions is a fundamental issue, when 35% of the EU buildings are over 50 years old.

CHESSE SETUP ensures that its system will have a low payback period and a reduced environmental impact compared with conventional systems, due to the low ecological footprint and the simplicity and availability of most of the used elements. The primary energy savings will be calculated using an LCA (Life Cycle Analysis) approach and will consider the embodied energy of all components. Then, the system performance will be verified by implementing the EU Environmental Technology Verification (ETV) pilot Program.

Through the sustainable development’s prism, we can argue CHESSE SETUP will have a green impact on the three elements of this concept: society, environment and economy.

2.2.3. Key messages

According to the project's content, and taking into account the general European framework, the key messages brought by CHESSE SETUP would be:

New system able to provide heating and DHW based on **hybrid solar panels, an energy storage tank and a heat pump** "smartly" connected to **interact with the local or national grid** in order to optimize the electricity demand

With an efficient **combination** of these 3 elements, CHESSE SETUP's solution will supply all the heating needs **all year long** as well as **reduce sharply the electricity**

Under a *Zero Energy Building* approach, CHESSE SETUP will **include other renewable energies** to back-up the system designed during the less-sunny months

The project aims to develop a tool able to **assess the economic viability** for different business models and different thermal energy integration

2.3. Engineering of the project

CHESSE SETUP is a consortium of ten different actors, coming from Spain, England, but also France, Germany and the Netherlands. A division of labour is planned and scheduled in the grant agreement already signed. The project is divided into seven work packages, including 4 technical ones, following the scheme bellow.

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Project management (WP1) along with communication activities (WP7) will last all along the 36-month implementation. Thus, those work packages will play a major role into CHESSETUP's achievements' diffusion.

The prior achievement of the project's engineering is a *sine qua none* condition to the dissemination activities' success. WP1 is the basis of CHESSETUP's internal communication through,

- the animation of the mailing list,
- the Drop Box's supervision,
- the holding of meetings every 6 months,
- the control of the deliverables' quality on time,
- the management of internal risks,
- the communication of the results to the consortium, and especially to WP7.

WP1 will ensure an efficient and cohesive group communication.

The variety of actors, backgrounds, and professions should be seen as richness in order to expand CHESSETUP's audience. According to the Grant Agreement, each member of the consortium has to raise awareness, to spread the project's key messages through its professional networks.

Figure 3- CHESSETUP: 10 different actors spreading the same message

The members have also been pleased to communicate their stakeholders' contact list in order to build the initial contact list of newsletters' recipients. The first newsletters and/or press releases will be sent to those identified stakeholders, and later on to the whole of new subscribers.

3. Dissemination strategy

Once set the project's scene and content, it is time now to think about how, when, and to who conveying the key messages. Talking about dissemination strategy is assuming objectives, and identifying channels of fulfilling them. The following part analyses stakeholders' engagement and details the dissemination tools that will be activated in order to spread awareness and spread CHESSETUP's messages.

The strategy should give an orientation on the following questions:

- What kind of needs does the project respond to?
- Who will use these results
- What benefits will be delivered and how much benefit?
- How will end users be informed about the generated results?

3.1. Strategy objectives

The Communication and Dissemination Plan is a tool to spread Chess Set Up achievements and to make it renowned as a suitable technical solution to build NZEB. Thus and as we have already said, the idea will be to raise awareness, in order to disseminate the achievements which will appear all along the 36 months of the project.

More specifically, the objectives are:

Raise awareness among urban planners and the building sector about CHESSETUP's mission and the benefits of integrated thermal systems for the design and renovation of the buildings.

Interact with other relevant European and National projects in creation of dissemination events and ensure synergies with other European strategies.

Develop a set of communication tools, activities and channels to reach the targeted audience (information notes, briefing notes, ...).

Publication of results and tools developed in the project.

Encourage the roll-out of the solution among private companies and cities and regions across Europe.

Web page for both partners and dissemination.

3.2. Target audience and users

If the dissemination plan objectives focus on the building sector and the European ecosystem, we must provide a detailed analysis of all the potential stakeholders. A precise knowledge of the audience that could be interested by the Chess Set Up system will help to target and adapt the content of or dissemination activities.

It has been decided to broaden the width of potential stakeholders, ranging from the building sector (identified since the beginning), to the civil society, a conceptual entity including non-technical recipients such as the media and end users.

3.3. Reaching our targeted audience

As it appears on the stakeholder's range, the diversity of the audience induces a differential treatment. In order to reach every stakeholder's category, we may adapt the content of the messages spread, as well as the media carrying it.

The communication channels will be:

- **The Website.** The flagship of the consortium. A website has already been created and will be an exhaustive overview of all the dissemination tools and communication actions. On the website will be published Chess Set Up's news items, the abstracts, scientific articles and deliverables, a timeline of CHESSE SETUP's Twitter account, the press releases, information about the clustering events in which Chess Set Up will take part or will organize. A "Frequently Asked Questions" (FAQ) heading will be edited, as well as and a contact formula in order to allow one-to-one communication.

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- **Social media and newsletters.** Twitter and LinkedIn accounts will be created in order to spread CHESSE SETUP's message, to raise awareness concerning Chess Set Up's ecosystem (energy efficiency, NZEB building, solar energy, smart cities...), and to join stakeholders' networks and groups. A newsletter will be sent at list every 6-months to the mailing-list composed of the initial stakeholders' list and the further subscribers.
- **Clustering activities.** The dissemination plan aims to raise awareness concerning the CHESSE SETUP's ecosystem, but also to enter CHESSE SETUP as a component of this ecosystem. Thus, clustering activities will be a central part of the dissemination plan. Clustering activities cover workshops' organization, participation in expositions, congress and conferences, or all events gathering potential stakeholders. CHESSE SETUP's presence could be having a conference and introducing the results or to have a stand.
- **The Press.** Along the 36-month implementation, 3 press releases will be edited, sent to press agencies and published on the website. The aim is to provide a clear message to all kind of media, in order to raise awareness concerning the project's objectives and achievements.

The same amount of divulgation articles will be written for publication in specialized revues. Those articles could be translated into four different languages, and the potential diffusors are identified in this document. Content will also be sent to specialized on-line revues or website in order to widen the scope of potential readers.

- **One-to-one communication, and local events.** The dissemination plan also allows and considers other types of communication, at a smaller scale. Depending on the implementation results, and the exchanges between CHESSE SETUP and the stakeholders, WP7 as well as the other CHESSE SETUP's members could be required to spend time with potential stakeholders in order to explain the implementation. Reunions could be held at a pilot's level to answer the users or suppliers' questions.

One-to-one communication is conceived both as answering questions, and to spread CHESSE SETUP's results to a very targeted audience. Dissemination work could aim to reach an identified stakeholder with a customised message (phoning, email, reunion). We could mention here the specific case of the briefing notes for the European Commission or the departments of energy.

On the other hand, if all the tools mentioned above do not succeed in providing a complete explanation of the project and of its goals, the contact formula published on the website will provide another recourse for the people.

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Each of these channels can be scalable for different solutions. Thus, CHESSE SETUP will involve its dissemination activities into every channel, and try to adapt the content, form and frequencies of the messages spread.

3.4. Stakeholder engagement

Ensure the effectiveness of the dissemination activities means identifying the stakeholder's engagement, the interest they could find into the project, and the best way to raise their awareness.

The following table sums up our analysis and will be the effectiveness guideline of the plan. An indicator of "tool relevance" has been drawn according to the stakeholders' interests, needs and habits (see Appendix A). This should help adjusting our communication strategy to our targeted audience.

Sector	Organization	Communication Channels																
		Linked In	Twitter	Newsletters	Workshops	Exhibitions	Conferences	Deliverables	News items	Video	Other documentation	Press releases	Scientific publications	Other articles (blog, mass media)	Local events	Conven's potential stakeholders	Explain the project's objectives	Briefing notes
Building sector	Architects	2	2	2	2	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
	Constructor groups	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2
	Retrofitting business	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1
Urban planners	Pub. Entities responsible of social housing programs	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	1
	Policy makers	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1
Installation providers	Manufacturers	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1
	Smart grids businesses	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1
University and R&D	Academia	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	3
	Related research programs	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1
European ecosystem	Departments of Energy/Environment	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1
	Public agencies	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1
Civil society	Media	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	1	3	2	1	1	2
	End users	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	3	1	1	3	1	1	1	1	1
Energy sector	Energy suppliers	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2
	Network managers	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1

Legend:

- 1: Poor relevance and efficiency
- 2: Relevant but average efficiency
- 3: Relevant and efficient

A further stakeholders' engagement analysis will be made, classifying them more thinly according to their level of interest and influence (Appendix B). As we consider that stakeholders' groups are not uniform, but heteroclitic, and that influence deals more with particular cases than activity sectors, this table will be made when we have a complete list of stakeholders' name at our disposal. More efficient communication actions could be extracted from this table, considering the catalyser effect of targeting influencers, and trying to correct the interest's lack.

3.5. Schedule

Dissemination activities are highly dependent on external (abstracts' acceptance) as well as internal factors (successful outcomes). However, it is necessary to have a roadmap to ensure a communication basis. The following timeline states the guaranteed dissemination activities program.

Dissemination plan

We must not forget that some activities will be held for certain all along the project's life.

- Social networking about CHESSE SETUP and its ecosystem will be held on a weekly basis.
- The website will be updated on a regular basis, providing the most relevant articles as possible.

Concerning the clustering activities and publications, if we could not ensure the project's acceptance, we can set objectives to fulfil:

- At list 5 publications in revues (3 divulgation articles and 2 scientific papers),
- At list 10-15 mentions of CHESSE SETUP on specialized websites,
- At list 2 workshops organized by CHESSE SETUP,
- At list 3 conferences organized by CHESSE SETUP,
- At list 3-5 events joined by CHESSE SETUP,
- At list 3 briefing notes for the EU Commission.

3.6. Resources

This document will be firstly delivered on Month 2, at the very beginning of the project. However, the dissemination strategy has been thought, and there are basic tools on which the further activities will be able to rely.

3.6.1. Human and financial resources

All the communication and dissemination activities will be considered within the commitment framework signed in the Grant Agreement concerning all five tasks from WP7.

3.6.2. Visual identity

The flagship of CHESS SETUP's visual identity will be its logo, shown below:

As a central communication tool, the logo itself conveys a message. The black and white squares represent a PV-ST solar panels chess game. The set of the four panels looks like a flower, epitomizing the environmental aims of the project. The orange circles around it stands for the sun, giving the project its original purpose. The ochre colour recalls the heat provided by the system. Finally, the logo is labelled with the project name, Chess Set Up, in a modern informatics-style police, remembering we deal with a smart city related project.

Moreover, a graphic charter is defined. It will be used in all the documents edited by Chess Set Up's members to provide a guiding light and to establish the project's visual identity.

3.6.3. Communication supports

Communication's flagship, the website uses the previously described visual identity.

As this channel will provide various kind of materials, addressing stakeholders with different levels of technicity, its layout must be clear and attractive. Besides, according to the stakeholder engagement table, this channel will be the most used one, and a

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flagship of the communication strategy. The website will be updated on a weekly basis to keep in touch with CHESSE SETUP's day-to-day affairs.

First of all, the website has to answer fundamental questions about the project: What? Who? Why? When? How?

Then, the headings are thought to host all the communicational tools introduced.

This channel will be further updated in order to be more suitable for different needs:

- A reserved access for the CHESSE SETUP members will be implemented. It would aim to make internal communication easier, as the posts will sum up the project's state of progress.
- A short video introducing briefly and visually the project will be uploaded on the website front-page in order to attract all the visitors and provide a graphical "frame" of it. This communicational tool will be well-fitted for non-technical stakeholders, but also for technical ones, as it could draw attention and lead them to go further into the project (the achievement of this milestone is subject to financial and human resources availability).

Also, additional specifications have been required by other members of the consortium:

- Make the simulation tool (from WP3) available for download as an open source asset;
- Interactive data base of the measures from WP4 (to be continuously uploaded).

In addition, CHESSE SETUP will also take over other virtual spaces: the social media and an emailed newsletter.

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CHESS SETUP will have LinkedIn and Twitter accounts (@ChessSetUp) using the project's logo, and the key messages registered in the accounts' introductions. Those communicational tools will be bidirectional: used to spread news items and achievements, and to meet potential stakeholders.

The messages' content will focus on the project's achievements, but also on the project's ecosystem, and the relevant news items which could interest stakeholders. Chess Set Up would be integrated in networks related to the following topics: green economy, sustainable development policies, NZE buildings (energy storage, heating systems), smart cities, and solar technologies. Synergies could be implemented with tied European projects (see chapter 3.6.6) via this channel allowing exchanges of information, but also audience support. Hence, CHESS SETUP's LinkedIn and Twitter accounts will also be updated on a weekly basis in order to anchor the project in its natural ecosystem.

The biannual newsletter will sum up the most relevant news items in different headings such as "*CHESS SETUP Life*" or "*About Smart Buildings' World*".

According to the stakeholder contact list's evolutions, a bias could be introduced into the newsletter's content in order to be as relevant as possible. Moreover, we can also imagine numerous targeted editions of it along the project's life.

Also, to support CHESS SETUP's presence in events, conferences, or for one-to-one exchanges, communication medium will be edited.

Brochures and leaflets will be conceived as a fast tool to give an overlook of the system implemented, and the potential scope of its achievements.

On Month 3 (August 2016), a leaflet and a brochure will be edited and released. They will be sent to every CHESS SETUP member so they could easily distribute them to potential stakeholders and a dematerialized version will be ready to download on the website.

They will be printed on request, and according to the upcoming events. To avoid any paper waste, and taking into account the level of dematerialization of the communication activities, there will not be any quota or impressions' objective.

3.6.4. Stakeholders contact list

As mentioned above, every CHESS SETUP member had to fill the stakeholders' table in order to make their networks available for the consortium (find it attached in Appendix C). CHESS SETUP's initial audience is the set of ten combined professional networks distributed as follows.

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This table is not an exhaustive list of CHESSETUP's contacts. It is only an overview of it, as all the data is not available at Month 2. This list will grow along the implementation and the stakeholders' meeting.

Moreover, CHESSETUP members gave preliminary information sheets about their own communication channels. Thus, we have an overview of the cumulative networking audiences, and privileged contact among definite media channels.

	Lavola		AEU Barcelona		Electric Corby		Sant Cugat	
	Frequency of activity	Nº of followers/users						
Website	Weekly	3000/year	Weekly	150/day	Weekly	250/month	Daily	898897/year
Twitter	Daily	2600	4-5/week	1390	Daily	374	4-5/day	2553
LinkedIn	Weekly	2410	3-4/week	2234	Weekly	378	N/A	N/A

Figure 4- Extract of the networking members' data

3.6.5. Clustering activities and revues

In order to reach our objectives, an analysis of the ecosystem's media and events has been made. Thus, we dispose of a list of conference and shows, as well as a range of revues potentially interested in spreading Chess Set Up's messages and a list of European related projects.

The events' table will be updated, as the project's duration is longer than the organizers' agenda. The following table introduces the targeted events that Chess Set Up could join. Their order of appearance stands for their priority level, relying on:

- The event's audience and relevance,
- The cost of joining the event (giving a conference or having a stand),
- The organization facilities (abstracts' deadline, place...).

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	International	Date	Location
1	EU Sustainable Energy Week 2017	Annual	
2	Sustainable City 2017	Annual	Spain
3	World Sustainable Energy Days 2017	Annual	Austria
4	IRES 2017	Annual	Germany
5	Euroheat and Power Congress 2017	Annual	Scotland
6	World Sustainable Build Conference 2020	Triannual	
7	Geo Power and Heat Summit	Last Edition: 2015	

	National	Date	Location
1	Greencities	Annual	Spain
2	Smart Grid-Smart City and intelligent building system	Annual	France
3	Energy storage: technologies and projects	Annual	Spain
4	Trade Show for the Energies and Sustainable Buildings	Annual	France
5	Dutch National sustainability Congress	Annual	Netherlands

Figure 5 – Specific European events related to CHESSE SETUP topics

In order to create synergies with other European projects dealing with the same topic and issues, an identification of this stakeholder's category has been made. As mentioned above, a cooperation among European projects could help backing communication activities, or providing information (through briefing notes).

EINSTEIN	Einstein project - Effective integration of seasonal thermal energy storage systems in existing buildings
MESSIB	Multisource Energy Storage System Integrated in Buildings - integrating four storage technologies (2 thermal and 2 electrical) into edification
DOF	District of the Future - Increasing energy efficiency at district level using ICT technologies
DREEAM	Demonstration of an integrated Renovation approach for Energy Efficiency At the Multi building scale
CREATE	Compact REtrofit Advanced Thermal Energy storage
REnnovates	Flexibility Activated Zero Energy Districts
BuildHEAT	Standardised approaches and products for the systemic retrofit of residential Buildings, focusing on HEATING and cooling consumptions attenuation.
TESSe2b	Thermal Energy Storage Systems for Energy Efficient Buildings. An integrated solution for residential building energy storage by solar and geothermal resources
Train-to-NZEB	Train-to-NZEB: The Building Knowledge Hubs
ZERO-PLUS	Achieving near Zero and Positive Energy Settlements in Europe using Advanced Energy Technology
HyTile	Sensitive integrated Solar Hybrid Roofing for historical buildings.
GREENHP	Next generation heat pump for retrofitting buildings
SDHp2m	Advanced policies and market support measures for mobilizing solar district heating investments in European target regions and countries
CoolHeating	Market uptake of small modular renewable district heating and cooling grids for communities
THERMOSTALL	High Performance Seasonal Solar Energy Latent Heat Thermal Storage Using Low Grade, Low Melting Temperature Metallic Alloys
SmartHeat	An intelligent modular domestic heating and hot water platform that enables effective integration and use of renewable energy systems
Hi-ThermCap	High-capacity and high-performance Thermal energy storage Capsule for low-carbon and energy efficient heating and cooling systems
FLEXYNETS	Fifth generation, Low temperature, high EXeRgY district heating and cooling NETworkS
PIPESTORE	A modular phase change material thermal store that enables optimal performance of renewable energy systems
PV/HP GENERATION	A Micro-generation System Using PV/heat-pipe Roof Modules
GREEN SOLAR CITIES	Global renewable energy and environmental neighbourhoods as solar cities
PAMELA	Phase change material slurries and their commercial applications (PAMELA)

	Grant Agreement signed
	On-going project
	Closed project

Figure 6 - List of "twin" projects

The dissemination plan mentions an objective of 10-15 publications about Chess Set Up in specialized revues. As the audience of this channel is composed of stakeholders with high interest in the project (see Appendix B table), it will be a suitable tool to spread CHESSE SETUP's achievements among technical recipients.

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English	French	Spanish	German	Deutsch
Energy and Buildings	Développement Durable et Territoire	Futureenergy	Natur	Energiegids
Solar Energy	EchoGéo	Ecoticias		
Renewable Energy Magazine	Nature Sciences Société	Retema		
Energy Conversion and Management	Education relative à l'environnement	L'Econòmic		
EuroScience	Revue du Génie et de la Science de l'Environnement	Ciudad Sostenible		
Revolve	Métropoles	Món sostenible		
		Revista Theknos		
		Energías Renovables		
		Grupo TecmaRed		

Figure 7 - Specialized revues

To widen the audience's range, abstracts, articles and press releases will also be sent to other media such as websites and blog. A list of the blogs which might be prepared to talk about Chess Set Up has been held. The list gathers revues' internet edition, but also personal blogs.

English	Spanish	French
Sustainable Build	Sostenible.cat	La Cité des Smart Cities
Market place of the European Innovation Partnership on Smart Cities and Communities	Smart Cities (es)	Le blog de l'habitat durable
Renewables International	Erenovable.com	Les énergies solaires
Renewable Energy World	Energias Renovables	Le blog énergie
New energy		EcoCo2
Architecture magazine		
High performing buildings		
Retrofit companies		
Alliance to save energy		
Energy Saving Trust		
Social housing		
Energy News (National Geographic)		
Construction Marketing Association blog		
How Stuff Works		

Figure 8 - Specialized websites/blogs

4. Monitoring and evaluation

From the dissemination plan depends CHES SETUP's posterity. As the implementation is supported by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 program, and the results potentially determining for the European goals and the sustainable development of the housing sector, the present plan's effectiveness shall be continuously monitored.

For this purpose, during the implementation phase of the dissemination, key performance indicators (KPI) will be monitored in order to redefine (if needed) the pre-established strategy. This real-time feedback will allow us to refine the ongoing/future communication activities with the aim of reaching the dissemination and communication objectives.

A first set of preliminary KPI's have been defined as follows:

TYPE OF CHANNEL	Echo	General
Social media/Newsletter	N° subscribers/followers Popularity of the messages Audience of the subscribers Initial meeting w/ stakeholders	Publications' frequency N° types of newsletters (adaptation to the public)
Website	N° direct contacts from form Questions asked N° documentation downloads N° views of the promotional video	Uploads' frequency FAQ's edition (Y/N) Infography edition Video (Y/N)
Clustering Activities	N° people attending presentation N° people stopping at the stand Initial meeting w/ stakeholders Relevant informations gathered N° people attending the kick off meeting N° people attending the final conference	N° abstracts sent N° attending event Time spent on strategic watch Time spent on workshops' organisation
Local events	N° people attending People's involvement	N° meetings organised Positive evaluation
One-to-one communication	N° people concerned N° of new contacts Relevant informations gathered	Average time spent answering Time spent canvassing potential stakeholders Follow-up of this exchanges
Press	N° edited N° publications in revues N° publications in generalist revues Audience of the publications	Abstracts, articles sent Contact with journalists/editors N° Press Releases

5. Conclusions

The strategy established in the present document aims to cover the above-mentioned network of stakeholders and groups of interest by spreading the precise key messages of CHESSE SETUP project. Thus, it will be mandatory to revise and update this plan in parallel with project achievements and progress. Also, objectives have been clearly defined as well as a first set of indicators that will guide this strategy and its associated activities to project dissemination success.

A preliminary SWOT analysis has been performed to lowering the risks that the project could face in terms of communication and dissemination activities:

Therefore, it will be crucial to begin developing the first activities (such as target audience identification) in the early stages of the project in order to efficiently raise awareness among the sectors related to CHESSE SETUP topics. Then, the customization of the approaches for each target group will be clearly pre-defined and implemented in a cost-effectively way.

Appendix A - Stakeholders' engagement

1. Process

The figure below schematizes the stakeholder's analysis process (with the example of the Architects case). By identifying the stakeholders' interests and needs, we deduce the most relevant channels to use.

2. Stakeholder group's analysis

The following table is extracted from the general table listing all the stakeholder group's analysis, following the above-mentioned identification process.

Types and sub-types of stakeholder	Interest in the project	Level of technicity	Information needed	How to provide it?
Building sector		2		
<i>Architects</i>	Conceive modern buildings that will have to be NZE, Find esthetical and discreet designs suitable to the Chess Setup's system	2	Dimensions and type of components of the system, geothermal and climatic determinants	Reves, networking, clustering activities
<i>Constructor groups</i>	Propose a NZEB supply with low payback and low K investments, Establish urban complex's supplies around a centralized system	2	Dimensions and type of components of the system, geothermal and climatic determinants	Reves, networking, clustering activities
<i>Retrofitting business</i>	Propose a NZEB supply with low payback and low K investments suitable to existing/historical buildings	2	Dimensions and type of components of the system, geothermal and climatic determinants	Reves, networking, clustering activities
Urban planners		2		
<i>Pub. Responsible of social housing programs</i>	Find economical solutions to achieve the European objectives, propose healthy housing solution with low cost	2	Cost of the system, overall advantages for the users, the finances, the environment.	Information notes, business model, final report (website, end meeting)
<i>Policy makers</i>	Find solutions to achieve the European objectives, incite the spreading of those solutions among the society	2	Cost of the system, overall advantages for the users, the finances, the environment.	Information notes, business model, final report (website, end meeting)
Installation providers		2		
<i>Manufacturers</i>	Discover efficient ways of conceiving their products, connect to opportunities	2	Capacity of the system, engineering informations	Scientific publications (website), clustering activities
<i>Smart Grid related companies</i>	Conceive monitoring and data systems	2	Capacity of the system and the software, energetic efficiency, users acceptance	Scientific publications (website), clustering activities
Academia/Research programs	Study the results to launch further research programs, to theorize other systems, to teach them	3	Engineering of the system, monitoring, results of the further implementations	Publications, final results (=website), clustering activities
European Ecosystem		2,5		
<i>Departments of Energy/Environment</i>	Find solutions to achieve the European objectives, and incite to their spreading, gather the information, evaluate and regulate the system	2	Achievements, further implementations, overall cost and environmental profit of the system.	Networking, clustering activities, publications, information notes
<i>Public Agencies</i>	Find solutions to achieve the European objectives, and incite to their spreading, gather the information and edit communication messages and reports	3	Achievements, further implementations, overall cost and environmental profit of the system.	Networking, clustering activities, publications, information notes
Civil society		1		
<i>Media</i>	Gather the information, and translate it to their public, convey a message	1	Understand the objectives, the general mecanisms, achievements and impacts of the system	Networking, website, press releases, clustering activities
<i>Final users</i>	Understand the system providing them heating and DHW in order to accept it better, and explain it outside. Live in an healthy environment.	1	Understand the objectives, the general mecanisms, achievements and impacts of the system	Local events, website (FAQ)
Energetic sector		2,5		
<i>Energy suppliers</i>	Imagine contracts of purchase and sale, anticipate the electric demand, f	2	Monitoring and output of the system	Publications, final results (=website, one-to-one communication)
<i>Network power controller</i>	Anticipate the electricity flows on the network, lower the power needs a	3	Monitoring and output of the system	Publications, final results (=website, one-to-one communication)

Appendix B - Stakeholders' mapping

Template of the stakeholder's interest and influence mapping.

Appendix C - Stakeholders' contact table

The following table has been sent to all the consortium members in order to set the preliminary stakeholders' list.

Types and sub-types of stakeholder	Name	Location	Contact name	Contact email	Relative CSU member	Interest in the project
Building sector						
<i>Architects</i>						
<i>Constructor groups</i>						
<i>Retrofitting business</i>						
Urban planners						
<i>Pub. Responsible of social housing programs</i>						
<i>Policy makers</i>						
Installation providers						
<i>Manufacturers</i>						
<i>Smart Grid related companies</i>						
Academia/Research programs						
European Ecosystem						
<i>Departments of Energy/Environment</i>						
<i>Public Agencies</i>						
Civil society						
<i>Media</i>						
<i>Other groups of interest</i>						
Energy sector						
<i>Energy suppliers</i>						
<i>Energy network managers</i>						

